

Strategies to be Adopted in Higher Education Institutions to Enhance Admission Demand

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Abstract

To face global and local competition and to enhance admission demand for sustainability, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies (SIMS) has adopted several innovative strategies and this paper consists of such strategies adopted for improving the quality, and attract more students admission to its courses. These strategies include institutional objectives and core values, choice of courses, publicity strategy, criteria adopted for admission, institutional review, admission policy, catering student diversity, strategy to assess the students' needs, strategy for effective implementation of curriculum, institutional strategy to supplement the university's curriculum, strategies adopted to bridge the knowledge gap, student-centric learning process, institutional strategy to nurture critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students, technology adoption strategy, strategy on innovative teaching approaches/methods adopted, library resources strategy, strategy adopted to complete the curriculum, faculty re-charge strategy, strategies adopted by the institution in enhancing the teacher quality, quality monitoring strategy, faculty evaluation strategy used for improving the quality of the teaching-learning process, curriculum supplement & enrichment strategies, strategy of introducing new programmes/courses, and innovations and best practices in teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Admission strategy, quality monitoring strategy, technology adoption strategy, library resources strategy.

Introduction

After globalization and opening up the education opportunity for private sector and foreign universities, higher education became more competitive and challenging. Due to enhanced demand for higher education in developing countries, many players entered this field and higher education became further competitive. The only way to withstand in those competition is to improve the quality (Harvey and Green, 1993, Hill, 1995, Hill et al. 2003, Joseph et al. 2005) and balancing customer needs and standards of higher education (Cathy et al. 2012). To face such competition and to enhance admission demand for sustainability, Srinivas Institute of management Studies (SIMS) has adopted several innovative strategies and the paper consists of such strategies adopted for improv-

ing the quality, and attract more students admission to its courses. These strategies include institutional objectives & core values, choice of courses, publicity strategy, criteria adopted for admission, institutional review, admission policy, catering student diversity, strategy to assess the students' needs, strategy for effective implementation of curriculum, institutional strategy to supplement the university's curriculum, strategies adopted to bridge the knowledge gap, student-centric learning process (Wright and Neil, 2002), institutional strategy to nurture critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students, technology adoption strategy, strategy on innovative teaching approaches/methods adopted, library resources strategy, strategy adopted to complete the curriculum, faculty re-charge strategy, strategies adopted by the institution in enhancing the teacher quality (Srikanthan and Dalrymple, 2002), quality monitoring strategy (Srikanthan and Dalrymple, 2003), faculty evaluation strategy used for improving the quality of the teaching-learning process (Neill and Palmer, 2004), curriculum supplement & enrichment strategies, strategy

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of introducing new programmes/courses, strategy of marketing existing courses (Kotler, 1985) and innovations & best practices in teaching & learning (Manual for self-study report of Affiliated colleges, 2013).

Srinivas Institute of Management Studies (SIMS) is offering two years (4 semester) AICTE recognized M.B.A programme with specialization in Marketing, Finance, Human Resource Management, and Production and systems with an annual intake of 120, three years MCA program with intake of 60 students. Both the programmes are affiliated to Mangalore University. The college also offers three years degree programs Bachelor of Computer Applications (BCA), Bachelor degree in Business Management (BBM) and Bachelor of Commerce (B.Com.). All three courses are affiliated to Mangalore University. The college is admitting 180 students for BBM program, 150 students for BCA program and 75 students for B.Com. The college is having a state-of-the-art computer lab with free internet connectivity and adequate software, comprehensive library with about 25,000 textbooks and about 90 research journals/magazines, and an active placement cell. The college is adapting various teaching & learning methods like case studies, group dynamics, written projects, group discussions, videos, computer-assisted learning packages, role plays, in-basket exercises, and simulations exercises. The college also conducts industry visits for MBA and MCA students to have real contact with the world. In order to enhance students communication ability, networking and research perception, a 8 weeks summer project is being arranged. The college arranges monthly workshops to create competitive advantage through effective management education. With the unique facilities like net library through free internet through Wi-Fi, regular classes and student presentations using LCD projectors, regular distribution of Business line news paper to each student and result oriented co-curricular activities like business case analysis, group discussions, computer based simulation programmes, VCD talks of eminent Management gurus, Business news analysis, Industry visits and interaction with Industry experts, the institution is striving to impart value added education to its students, the institution is committed to provide a learning environment of a high order to its students and qualify them to be competent, skillful and professionals in serving in industries or in any organizations. The College has been identified as one of the few top B-schools in India. The College has registered 100% academic result with abundant distinctions & first classes in University examinations since its inception and the alumni's are well settled in their life in various Prestigious positions in the society. The college is located at Srinivas campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, and using industry oriented curriculum and experimental learning model the college is doing an effort to produce useful innovative managers to industries.

Methodology

Various strategies to enhance admission demand

Higher education institutions adopt various strategies to differentiate their courses in terms of the values seen by their students. This will help them to attract more students and maintain good admission demand for sustainability. **Figure 1** shows the block diagram of various strategies adopted by higher education institutions to enhance admission demand. **Table 1** lists various criteria's used under these strategies to improve the brand name of higher education institutions.

Results and Discussion

Various strategies used at SIMS: A case study

Some of the strategies and their criterion's used in SIMS are discussed as a case study in following sections.

(1) Institutional Objectives & Core Values

(a) Institutional Objectives

- To make available world class education with an Indian ethos to the student community.
- To create centre of excellence imparting quality education.
- To offer to the society /industry, academically empowered and ready for the job professionals in diverse fields.
- To foster research and dissipate research findings for the all round development of the nation and community at large.
- To contribute to nation building by generating a pool of human resources trained in science, technology, humanities, management, education and research.
- To maintain dynamic equilibrium between the various educational institutions and the economic, socio-cultural and ecological environment.

(b) Core Values

1. Team Work
2. Respect
3. Responsibility
4. Ethics
5. Etiquette
6. Social Service
7. Communication, Character & Competency

Table 1. List of different criteria's under various strategies used for enhancement of admission demand

Sl. No.	Strategies Adopted	Criteria used in each strategies
1	Institutional Strategies	(1) Institutional Objectives & Core Values (2) Choice of Courses (3) Publicity Strategy (4) Criteria Adopted for Admission (5) Admission policy (6) Catering student diversity (7) Institutional strategy to nurture critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students (8) Technology adoption Strategy (9) Faculty re-charge strategy (10) Faculty evaluation strategy used for improving the quality of the teaching-learning process :
2	Student Centric Strategies	(1) Institutional Strategy to supplement the University's Curriculum (2) Student-centric Learning Process (3) Curriculum enrichment strategies (4) Strategy for effective implementation of curriculum (5) Strategy adopted to complete the curriculum :
3	Quality Enhancement Strategies	(1) Strategies to improve teachers quality (3) Strategies adopted by the institution in enhancing the teacher quality (3) Quality Monitoring Strategy
4	Innovative Strategies	(1) Strategies adopted to bridge the knowledge gap (2) Strategy on innovative teaching approaches/methods adopted (3) Library resources strategy (4) Identifying & implementing best practices
5	Competitive Strategies	(1) Introducing new programmes/courses (2) Improvement in Education Model (3) Improvements in Examination System (4) High salaried campus placement
6	Other Strategies	(1) Attractive infrastructure (2) Sports & Games facility (3) Good, hygienic cafeteria & Hostel facility (4) High tech environment (5) Industry tie-up

8. Techno-savvy & Scientific Thinking
9. Quest for Excellence
10. Courage to Innovate

The institutional objectives are translated into action and communicated in the following ways:

- The students receive quality education in a disciplined environment.
- The teachers are busy, motivated and academically oriented.
- The staff feels proud to work in a harmonious work place and lead a satisfied living.
- The parents of students are confident that their children are

in safe hands and they build a career.

- The neighboring community is happy with an institution for higher studies in their locality. They are also beneficiaries of the social service activities of the institute.
- The university is satisfied with a well functioning institution affiliated to it.
- The management is happy with the impact it creates in the society towards higher education and the opportunity provided to youngsters to groom their career of choice and providing jobs to many qualified youngsters in their institution.
- Other colleges find their staff and students in healthy competition.

Table 2. Details of self-financing courses at Srinivas Institute of Management Studies

Sl. No.	Name of the Course	Mode of admission	Curriculum	Tuition Fee	Minimum Teacher Qualification
1	MBA	Admission test	Credit based semester system	50,000	P.G. with 5 years experience or Ph.D. with two years experience
2	MCA	Admission Test	Credit based semester system	50,000	P.G. with 5 years experience or Ph.D. with two years experience
3	MSW	Admission Test	Credit based semester system	20,000	P.G. with 5 years experience or Ph.D. with two years experience
4	BBM	Marks in Qualifying Exam	Credit based semester system	25,000	P.G. with 2 years experience
5	BCA	Marks in Qualifying Exam	Credit based semester system	20,000	P.G. with 2 years experience
6	B.Com	Marks in Qualifying Exam	Credit based semester system	20,000	P.G. with 2 years experience

The Government is satisfied that the institute is sharing its goal of developing the youth to contribute to the nation.

The institute runs post-graduate programme in Business Management, Computer Applications, and Social Work and under-graduate programmes in Business Management, Computer Applications and Commerce. These are very well in terms of relevance to the country's developmental needs and human resource requirements. Industrial revolution was an event of the past, but industrialization continues to be the solution for developmental needs of goods, products, money and employment. The global trend is towards managing professionally, business ventures big and small. This should go hand in hand with every new business/industry or service facility launched. When the prime institute's products are leaning towards lucrative career in the west, the shortage has to be supplemented by private sector institutions. Computer application professionals have enormous scope ahead in this era of information technology. All systems in future would be computer based. Social work ensures that the pressure of technology should be balanced with social development and justice. There is need for professional social workers to work for the disadvantaged, having concern for environment and value orientation.

The institution communicates its objectives & goals to the students and other stakeholders through College website, Prospectus, College Calendar, Brochure, Alumni Association, Students meetings, Display boards in the college campus, Study Materials provided to the Students.

(2) Choice of Courses

All the programmes offered by the institution are self-financed programmes. The particulars of these courses with regards to admission, fee structure, teacher qualification, etc. are given **Table 2**.

(3) Publicity Strategy

The institution gives wide publicity for its admission to various courses. The following are the mainly adopted methods.

(a) Prospectus

Prospectus and multi colour information brochure are dispensed

at the college office. The prospectus contains information on various courses, admission requirements & eligibility, facilities, history of the institution, course details, photos for a glance of the infrastructure, job opportunities, and information about tie-up with banks for education loan. The prospectus also contains information about institutional tie-up with foreign institutions for further studies.

(b) Institutional website

Srinivas Group of Colleges has a website namely www.srinivasgroup.com which is comprehensive and covers all details regarding the institute very prominently. Admission eligibility, course requirement, curriculum and admission procedure are intended to be publicized through the website. It also provide details on the following : syllabus, evaluation, admission requirements, prescribed fees, duration of each course so as to give a clear information to the potential applicants. The infrastructure of the college and the facilities like LCD projectors fitted in each class, comfortable seating arrangements in the classroom, spacious classrooms, lighting and fan fittings are conveyed through the website visuals. It also contain rules and regulations applicable to all the courses as specified by the University. The profile of each individual faculty enables the students to locate his/her area of interest and field of specialization. Training and placement facility which is an integral part of students interest is also highlighted in the website. This is updated before admissions every year so that potential aspirants can access needed information easily.

The college website highlights why and how Srinivas Institute of Management Studies is different from other institutions in terms of academic facilities and innovativeness in idea generation.

(c) Advertisement in regional/national news papers

Direct advertisements are given during admission season in leading newspapers prominently.

The college conducts various programmes which will be high-lighted in local newspapers as well as local TV channels which will fetch publicity to the courses and the college for enhancing the admission.

Table 3. Eligibility criteria for the admission to the offered courses

Sl. No.	Name of the Course	Cut-off Marks (%) for Merit	Admission Test
1	MBA	50 % aggregate Marks in any Graduation	50% Govt. Quota through PGCET Counseling 50% Management Quota through either MAT/K-MAT/
2	MCA	50 % aggregate in Graduation with Maths/ Computer Science in Graduation	50% Govt. Quota through PGCET Counseling 50% Management Quota through either MAT/K-MAT/
3	MSW	45 % aggregate Marks in any Graduation	50% Govt. Quota through PGCET & Counseling 50% Management Quota through Written Test Conducted by the College
4	BBM	35 % aggregate in 12th Standard	Written Test Conducted by the College by following Roster system
5	BCA	35% aggregate in 12th Standard	Written Test Conducted by the College by following Roster system
6	B.Com.	35% aggregate in 12th Standard	Written Test Conducted by the College by following Roster system

(d) Other Publicity Strategies

- The college is an approved test centre for K-MAT exam, for which generally about 1000 candidates sit for the examination in an year. They come to know about the courses run by the college and interested students will seek admission in to the college for them self or for their peers.
- The college is an approved test centre for the international exams like TOEFL which is conducted at weekly intervals. This provides opportunity for gaining admission to the various courses.
- The college is an examination centre for distance mode of studies for Universities like Annamalai and Kuvempu University. Candidates, who come to take examinations here, get informed of the college and its courses thereby drawing potential aspirants for admission.
- The college is a regular test centre for many institutions such as banks, other govt. exams like KAS etc. This also provides a means of publicity to attract admissions.
- The college conducts mega job fair for differently qualified youth in association with Human Resource Development Centre of Govt. of Karnataka every year. Hosting such events also give publicity and attract admissions.
- Srinivas Institute of Rural Reconstruction Agency (SIRRA) which is an NGO functioning under the college conducts community programmes through which many people come to know about the college, courses, and admission.
- The college also take part in several education fairs held in different parts of the country to attract admissions.
- Banners are put up in the vicinity of the institute marking the commencement of admission for public view.
- Educational consultants spread the information on the college and courses far and wide.

(4) Criteria Adopted for Admission

Admission to the following professional courses are made with cut-off percentage marks at the entry level and admission test for eligibility as shown in following **Table 3.**

Admission Policy

- The college admits SC/ST students to various courses over and above the required minimum number set by the existing admission regulations.
- SC & ST students admitted to various courses under management seats are also provided concession at par with similar students admitted through Govt. quota.
- As per the admission regulations, the College allow relaxation of 5 % marks for entry level eligibility for the students belonging to SC/ST category.
- The College supports SC/ST students to utilize the boarding facility of Govt. Hostels keeping in view their affordability.
- The College promotes and guides the SC/ST students to avail scholarships and other benefits offered by Govt. and Quasi Govt. institutions.
- Out of the 50% seats reserved under Govt. quota, reservation of seats is also extended to OBC and the college strictly follows the roster system in admissions.
- Fee concession is also provided to the students admitted from OBC groups.
- The college follows a policy to support the differently abled applicants, provided they meet the minimum eligibility criteria.
- Students from economically weaker sections are attracted to seek admission to the college by availing financial loans

Table 4. Years 2012 student profile

Sl. No.	Course	Hindus (%)	Muslims (%)	Christian (%)	Others (%)
1	MBA	64	20	15	1
2	MCA	76	8	16	-
3	MSW	72	12	10	6
4	BBM	30	60	8	2
5	BCA	52	23	23	2

Table 5. Years 2013 student profile

Sl. No.	Course	Hindus (%)	Muslims (%)	Christian (%)	Others (%)
1	MBA	68	18	14	-
2	MCA	78	4	18	-
3	MSW	73	12	11	1
4	BBM	34	56	10	-
5	BCA	59	19	21	1
6	B.Com.	29	62	8	1

from banking institutions with low interest to be repaid after completion of the course and obtaining employment. For this purpose, an MOU has been signed with several Public sector banks.

- The college believes that opportunity to minority promotes national integration which is reflected in its admission policy and student profile. **Table 4** and **Table 5** gives a profile of the students admitted to various courses during the years 2012 and 2013 respectively.
- Gender and regional balance is kept in mind for admission to various courses as revealed in **Table 6** and **Table 7** for the years 2012 and 2013 respectively.

Catering Student Diversity

The institutions effort to cater to the needs of differently-abled students and ensure adherence to government policies in this regard :

- Two seats in each of the courses is reserved for orthopedically challenged students. If there is no eligible applicant during a particular year, it is merged into the general quota.
- There is ramp provision for upstairs in addition to lift facility.
- Provision for additional time in writing the internal exams and University Exams.

(7) Strategy for Effective Implementation of Curriculum

For effective implementation of the curriculum designed and provided by the affiliating university, the institution develop and deploys action plans which integrates time, quality, quantity and accountability. The key elements of the action plan are the followings:

1. Academic Calendar - To plan the academic year, Academic calendar is prepared every semester. The calendar reflects major events, programmes and activities to be taken up at the appropriate time.
2. Teaching plan – A detailed plan of the syllabus divided session-wise to ensure that time is evenly distributed for implementing the curriculum.
3. Teachers Diary – This is a work book maintained by each faculty wherein the particulars of each session conducted is entered with time, date, session number, topic and accessories used to ensure accountability.
4. Study Material – This is a compilation of relevant readings simplified and provided in thematic sequence which ensures that the entire quantity of the information prescribed for the course is conveyed.
5. Performance Appraisal - Periodic appraisal of the faculty make sure that they deliver the curriculum qualitatively and adequately well.

Although the institute follows the curriculum set by the University, the institute takes a proactive role through conducting curriculum improvement workshops and contributing to influence the curriculum design and development process at the University level. Feedback collected from students, alumni, academic peers, visiting faculty, resource persons for guest lectures and employers surface in these workshops. Recently, the University has consulted the college to radically redesign the obsolete syllabus of MBA program which was in vogue for 15 years and this was accomplished successfully. Similar efforts have been taken up for MCA, BCA and BBM programs. During these years the college was supplementing the curriculum deficiency through Certification programmes & Institutional Dual specialization opportunities to fill the knowledge gap between Institution and the Industry.

(8) Institutional Strategy to supplement the University's Curriculum

Institutions goals and objectives are focused on enhancing knowledge, skills and readiness to be absorbed in the job market. By keeping this in mind, the institution supplement the University's curriculum by variety of means :

- Curriculum delivery & pedagogy
- Skill development Package
- Exposure visits
- Certification Programmes
- Workshops

Table 6. Student In-take region-wise during the year 2012

Name of the Course	Gender %		Mangalore	Other parts of Karnataka	Other States	Other Countries
	Male	Female				
M.B.A.	65	35	27	28	65	-
M.C.A.	62	38	34	7	59	-
M.S.W.	64	36	9	74	17	-
B.B.M.	88	12	10	0	80	10
B.C.A.	75	25	16	3	81	-

Table 7. Student In-take region-wise during the year 2013

Name of the Course	Gender %		Mangalore	Other parts of Karnataka	Other States	Other Countries
	Male	Female				
M.B.A.	66	34	16	22	62	-
M.C.A.	44	56	18	22	60	-
M.S.W.	70	30	33	60	7	-
B.B.M.	93	7	4	1	93	2
B.C.A.	66	34	11	1	88	-

- Employability Trainings
- Industry-Institution Interface Programmes
- Field Visits
- Seminars & Conferences
- Guest Lectures
- Programmes under “Vivekananda Study Circle”
- NPTEL Video Lecture
- Value Addition Classes
- Imparting Messages Celebration of National/International Days
- Encouragement to take up EdX University Programs

- Troubleshooting Skills
- Android Application Development Skills
- Business Correspondence
- Spoken English
- Public speaking
- Program organizing
- Personality Building
- Time Management
- Communication Skills
- Leadership Skills
- Human Relationship Skills
- Soft Skills

(1) Curriculum delivery & pedagogy

The academic curriculum of the University in respect of all the courses is imparted systematically and well structured through :

- Session wise teaching plan
- Comprehensive study material prepared exactly according to the syllabus.
- Periodic internal Examination
- Topic based assignments
- Student presentations
- Case study analysis
- Student feedback
- Research Projects
- Field Practicum
- Laboratory based Practicals
- Thematic Fest
- Forum Activities

These activities/models enriches the curriculum set by the University and helps to integrate the institutions goals and objectives.

(2) Skill development Package

The following skill development programmes offered as a package as part and parcel with the curriculum

- Fund Raising
- Innovative ideas in Marketing
- Business Communication
- Effective Presentation
- Problem solving
- Team Building
- Entrepreneurship & Small business Planning
- Application software development Skill
- Website development & Design Skill
- Fund Raising Skill
- Team Presentation Skill

(3) Exposure visits

The college provides opportunity for exposure visit to gain first-hand knowledge. Some of them are:

- Orientation programmes
- Industry visits
- Study tours
- International educational visits
- Student exchange programmes

(4) Certification Programmes

The college is conducting various certificate programmes to bridge the gap between University curriculum and industry requirements. Some of the certificate programmes which are regular in feature are listed below:

(a) MBA Program

- Certificate course in Online Investment
- Certificate course on quantitative analysis using MATLAB/OCTAVE
- Certificate course on Investment Banking
- Certificate course in Cloud computing
- Certificate course in Android Mobile Applications
- Certificate course in Retail Marketing & Brand Management
- Certificate course in SPSS /PSPP statistical software
- Certificate Course in Computer Application (Tally, Excel, & Access)
- Certificate Course in R-Statistical Computing for Business Analytics
- Certificate Course in Blue Ocean Strategy and Green Business
- Certificate Course in Animation & Visual Effects
- Certificate Course on Mobile Business & Mobile banking

(b) MCA Program

- Certificate course in Animation & Visual Effects
- Certificate course in Strategic management in IT Sector
- Certificate course in Enterprises Resource Planning
- Certificate course in Entrepreneurial Development Programme
- Certificate course in R – Statistical Computing & Graphics for Business Analytics
- Certificate course in Cyber Law & IT security

(c) MSW Program

- Certificate course in HRD
- Certificate course in Counseling
- Certificate course in Human Rights
- Certificate course in NGO Management
- Certificate course in Industrial & Labour Laws

(d) BBM, BCA, B.Com Programs

- Certificate course in Spread Sheet Techniques
- Certificate course in E-Business Website Development
- Certificate course in Business & Communication soft skills
- Certificate course in Linux & Open Source Software
- Certificate course in Hardware & Networking
- Certificate course in Tally – Accounting software
- Certificate course in Animation

(5) Workshops

The institution organizes workshops of varying duration for all the courses of study. This will supplement the University curriculum gap with the institutions goals and objectives. A list of such workshops is listed below:

(a) MBA Program

- Workshop for preparing ICWA Aspirants
- Workshop on Corporate Yoga & Mind Control
- Workshop on Business Etiquettes
- Workshop on Nanotechnology Commercialization & Business Opportunities
- Workshop on Disaster Management
- Workshop on ERP Modules Applications & Vendors
- Workshop on Mobile Business & Mobile Banking

(b) MCA Program

- Workshop in Android Operating System & Application Development
- Workshop on PHP and MySQL
- Workshop on Stress Management
- Workshop on Cloud Computing
- Workshop on E-Business website development
- Workshop on Quantitative Analysis using MATLAB/OCTAVE

(c) MSW Program

- Workshop on Book Review Techniques
- Workshop on Essay Writing Practice
- Workshop on Gender sensitization
- Workshop on News Clippings Analysis & Integration
- Workshop for Character & Spiritual Development

(6) Employability Trainings

- Competitive exam training
- Interview preparedness
- Effective Decision making
- SWOT Analysis
- Oral & Written Communication
- Problem Solving
- Work Ethics

(7) Industry-Institution Interface Programmes

Various programmes are planned, implemented and promoted for Industry-Institution Interface.

- Industry Projects
- Guest lectures by Industry Experts
- Campus Recruitment
- Summer Placement
- Block Placement
- Mentorship Programs by Industry Managers
- Round Table Interaction with Entrepreneurs & Industry Experts
- Stories of Successful Entrepreneurs
- Development of Industry related Business cases
- Consultancy services

(8) Field Visits

- Orientation Visits
- Community Surveys
- Regular Field Practicum
- Social service activities

(9) Programmes under “Vivekananda Study Circle”

- Awareness Programmes on various social, moral, ethical principles
- Special lectures to instill moral and ethical values in life

(10) NPTEL Video Lecture

NPTEL Video lectures on Business Management, Social Science and Computer Science & IT are shown to the students periodically to enrich and supplement the University Curriculum.

(11) Value Addition Classes

Each theory paper has an extra chapter at the end, focusing on value building which is beyond the limits of curriculum offered by the University.

(12) Imparting Messages by Celebration of National/International Days

Days such as International Water Day, Health Day, Mothers day, Environment day, Human Rights day, Climate day etc. are observed through conducting talks & community awareness processions.

(13) Encouragement to take up edX University Programs

In order to enhance global competencies, the Institution encourages its students and faculty members to take up various Free video online courses from edX University which is a Joint Venture of Harvard University & MIT.

(9) Strategies Adopted to Bridge the Knowledge Gap

The College offers variety of Bridge/Remedial/Add-on/Enrich-

ment Courses to bridge the knowledge gap of the enrolled students and to enable them to cope with the programme of their choice like :

- Bridge course in Mathematics for MBA students
- Add-on course in Economics for MBA students
- Add -on course in Accountancy for MBA students with science background
- Enrichment course in Computer Science for all the PG students
- Remedial course in English Language for Under graduate students.
- Tutorial classes are engaged for weak students individually.
- Faculty identify weak students on the basis of class test papers and internal exams.
- Sometimes, students also approach faculty individually with doubts in any subject handled by the corresponding faculty. Non teaching hours are spent on giving special attention to them.
- The college functions for extended hours on all Saturdays, particularly to provide opportunity to facilitate tutorial sessions.
- The mentor chart used during counseling of the students provide source for identifying weak students who require tutorial sessions.

At the beginning of the semester students are divided in small groups and placed under each faculty for mentoring. This is widely done in undergraduate programme. Students fill in a Proforma known as mentor chart which conveys essential basic information pertaining to the personal and family details of the student. The mentors identify the strength and weaknesses of the students and guide the students throughout their period of study focusing on rectifying mistakes without fault finding attitude. Additionally, weak students are recommended to be admitted in the college hostels situated nearby the college and faculty members are provided accommodation in the same hostel to provide mentoring services to the needy.

(10) Student-centric Learning Process

Details on the support structures and systems available for teachers to develop skills like interactive learning, collaborative learning and independent learning among the students to make learning more student-centric:

1. As per our model, each teaching session starts with an Entry Test and ends with Summarization by two students.
2. Most classes are participatory in beginning with brain storming to introduce the subject and elicit curiosity among the students.
3. Students are encouraged to express their doubts in classes.
4. Real life examples of leaders, companies and contacts are made use of.
5. Good books are reviewed and habit of additional reading is cultivated among the student community.
6. In the MBA course professional newspaper of business executives namely "Hindu Business Line /Economic Times" is subscribed and made use of by all the students.
7. Assignment and student presentation are obligatory for students in all subjects.
8. Lecturing is the primary method of teaching.

9. LCD is fitted in all classrooms and used for teaching.
10. The institution provides interactive learning both among the students and assisted by invited resource persons.
11. Project based learning is a part of all the professional courses offered by the college. The project duration varies for different courses and most of the project reports are placed before the University for valuation and grading.
12. Computer assisted learning like simulations, experiential learning and seminars are frequently arranged to facilitate teaching-learning process.
13. Video clips are shown to enhance student interest in learning.

The following supportive structures and systems are available for teachers to develop skills like interactive learning, collaborative learning and independent learning among the students:

1. Structures:

- Conference room
- Library seatings
- Staff cabins
- Wi-Fi- Internet
- Computer Lab
- LCD & Video CD's
- Laptop computers as teaching information sharing gadgets

2. Systems:

- Group discussions
- Group Projects
- Team Assignments
- Team field work Practicum
- Organizing programs like Magma, Manthana, Manegma, Matrix, etc.
- Business News Paper Analysis in Groups

(11) Institutional Strategy to Nurture Critical Thinking, Creativity and Scientific Temper among the Students

The institution adopt following strategy to nurture critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students to transform them into life-long learners and innovators:

1. The institute identify talents/critical thinkers through participation in college activities and competitions, previous performance, participation in classroom discussions, group presentations, performance in semester end exam, participation & involvement in college programs, as well as their attitude and positive thinking.
2. Students are encouraged to boost their critical thinking through organizing and participating in programmes such as debate, competitions, and marketing exhibitions.
3. Students are also encouraged to participate in such competitions organized by other colleges. By providing information, giving attendance for classes lost, and financing sundry expenses, the institute promotes opportunity.
4. Students are also trained and guided in taking various competitive exams or entry into higher studies to specialize in chosen field.
5. The pedagogy is also styled to incorporate brainstorming sessions, entry test and recapitulations to nurture their critical thinking.
6. Research projects are encouraged and guided by the faculty

in all courses to develop creativity. Original contributions are encouraged for presenting in internal or external conferences.

7. EDP cell – The institution has a well developed entrepreneurship development cell. It conducts various activities to create awareness about entrepreneurship and to enhance the entrepreneurship skills among the students. The cell also conducts real time workshops where students get an opportunity to meet and interact with entrepreneurs and understand the real life problems. The students also get to discuss their business plans and make improvisations as per the recommendations given by the experts.
8. Internship and Project Committee – This committee encourages students to come up with ideas to have real time analysis of the problems at their area of study or industry. This will be done as a value addition for students' dissertation and internship work. It supports the students to develop case studies from their project work. It guides the students to develop model and solutions for the real time problems facing by the system or industry.
9. In MCA & BCA program, the students have to do mandatory software projects in a team of 4-5 members in order to sharpen their scientific temper. The best performing team is recognized and rewarded.
10. In MBA program, the finance division of the college conducts mock/virtual investment in share market. Based on one year monitoring, the best performance team will be rewarded.
11. Some of the Institutional Certificate programmes and workshops are identified and designed in such a way so that they become life-long learners and contributes to the society through their innovations.
12. The faculty members are constantly in the pursuit of upgrading themselves through acquiring additional qualification which inspire the students to become life-long learners.
13. The Opportunity given by way of encouraging subscription of news papers such as economic times and business line inculcate the habit of continued learners as long as they remain in the profession.

(12) Technology Adoption Strategy

The internet facility is provided in the campus through Wi-fi facility and networked computer labs. All classrooms are fitted with LCD projectors. Online classes are conducted using internet through wi-Fi.

1. LCD Projectors in each class: All the classrooms are fitted with LCD projectors. Faculty members use power point presentations to make classroom teaching more effective.
2. Audio Visual Aids: Audio Visual Aids are available in all the classrooms. Faculties are using video case studies, Movie clippings on management concepts, short films, and advertisements to explain certain topics more effectively.
3. WI-fi Campus: The campus is WI-fi enabled and has high Speed internet connectivity all the time. The faculty members are using internet facility to show real time information on industry, market and economy to the students in the class rooms.
4. Computer Labs: Computer labs used to make students to work on applications or internet for sourcing information.
5. TV: Television is installed in the college. Channels like Business news are played during the working hours. This will help the students to update themselves on the issues.
6. Digital Library: The faculty gives assignments, which would require students to use the digital library. The digital library enables the students to get research reports, case studies and any other relevant information required to complete the given assignments.
7. Public Address System : The classrooms & Auditorium are equipped with the public address system. Each classroom has a hand mike, collar mike and speakers. This helps the students and faculty members in their presentations, events like subject quiz and interactions in the classroom.
8. Surveillance Camera based Monitoring in the Campus : The centralized surveillance facility through fixed cameras in all classrooms give real time as well as recorded discipline in the class which helps monitoring for effective teaching.
9. Internet Based Library Services: The faculty members can avail various internet based library services such as accessing Various journals, Industry and research databases, other services from Delnet, EBSCO, etc. and internal library resource facilities which are linked to the institutional website.
10. National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NME-ICT): The faculty members are also availing information and services provided by National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology to prepare their study materials, lectures, and for advanced information.
11. High Speed Printers & Scanners Facility: Although sparingly used, the high speed printers and scanners are help the faculty to prepare multiple copies of case studies, business game etc.
12. NPTEL Video lectures: The college is encouraging to watch NPTEL video lecturers of IIT professors in the area of Computer Science, Business Management and social Science by downloading such videos and issuing the CD's of such lectures by College library.
13. Virtual Lab: Through simulation in virtual lab, e-learning is enhanced.
14. Digital Camera & Videography Facility: Through digital videography the classroom presentations are replayed to serve as feedback for improved learning.
15. Open Educational Resources:
 - Training of usage of Open Courseware by MIT & Sloan School of Business, IIM's, IIT's, IISC & IIIT's.
 - Training & usage of Open Source Software from AICTE websites.
 - Training on finding & usage of case studies from various free sources.
 - Training on online Job hunting through online job service providers.
 - Training on finding & usage of online text books from various websites.
 - Training on finding & usage of edX consortium online courses
16. Mobile Education: The college takes the faculty to the community/ industry as a part of learning through mobile education. Some of the Faculty Development Programs are conducted out-

side the college to enhance the effectiveness of training.

(13) Strategy on Innovative Teaching Approaches/methods Adopted

The various teaching –learning methods adopted in our Institute are:

1. Project based teaching: Faculty members give minor projects to group of students in different courses. On the completion of the projects, the team has to present the same and the faculty will award suitable marks/grades.
2. Lab based teaching: The Institute also has three computer labs with internet facility. The students are taken to the lab by the faculty members to provide them real time information on subjects.
3. Experiential learning: To improve the understanding of the subject case studies are framed jointly by faculty and students recalling their experience during visits and observations. This include managerial styles, superior and subordinate relationship, interpersonal communication, problem solving etc. For this purpose the students are sent on short-term assignments to the industry to have practical experience on working of industry.
4. Theatre based learning: The students are required to enact / explain certain concept through theater performance like role play, drama or short play on the assigned topics. Street plays are enacted in public locations to create awareness on social issues.
5. Simulation games: To give a real time experience of the business problems, simulation games are played in the classrooms. Students get a real feel of decision making, problem analysis and problem solving.
6. Video case study: Faculties assign students with special projects like making video case studies on specific topics.
7. Activity based learning: Students are involved in various activities and management games related to the topics from the subject.
8. Technology Based Learning: The internet, LCD, different application software etc. enable technology based learning.
9. Learning from Nature & Environment: Rural camp conducted for the students of social work and National Service Scheme are meant to learn from nature and environment.
10. Community Based Learning: Various activities conducted in the communities for MSW students and the activities conducted by the College NGO by name SIRRA provides community based learning.
11. Field Work Based Learning: MSW course require specific number of field work practicum as part of the curriculum. This is meant to sensitize the social work students to social issues.
12. Analytical Learning: Quantitative techniques of analysis are used in learning mostly by MCA students and also by finance specialization students of MBA.
13. Team Based Learning: The sum of individual performance is always less than teams performance. Hence in software development team based learning is made use of.
14. Observation based Learning: Demonstrations such as role play facilitates observation based learning.
15. Social service Based Learning: Community interactions help, build and develop interpersonal relationship through which social service is channelized.

(14) Library Resources Strategy

The library is stocked with subject related books, general management books, personality development books, books on competitive examinations, encyclopedias, National and International Journals, Magazines, newspapers both English and local language, CD and research reports. The institution also has digital library with access to journals through online data base like Delnet, EBSCO and JGATE. These resources are used in the following ways:

1. Library hour: One hour per week is designated as library hour in the timetable for P.G. Programs. The faculty members in-charge for the library hours introduce the students to various facilities available in the library databases from various websites to help students get in-depth information and knowledge about subjects taught in the class room. Business Management students are motivated by the faculty members to understand industry and market trends through publications, newspapers, journals and other available resources during the library hour. Publications and journals are available for reference during library hour for other courses.
2. Library based projects and assignments: The faculty members help students designs projects and assignments for which the students are required to refer to the resources available in the library.
3. Simulated learning through digital library: MBA Students are exposed to the stock market operations and trading through simulated online games available with the digital library of the college.
4. Library based research work: Students are exposed to various sources of online information and instructed to carry out the fundamental and technical analysis practically.
5. Faculty: The faculty members are extensively using the library and the digital library for class preparation and for research purposes. The faculty also refer the collection of business case studies for their class room discussions.
6. Library Information through College Website: The library provides old question papers as well as study materials of concerned subjects through college website so that students and faculty members can access them from their home whenever required. Students and faculty members can also find availability of textbooks and project reports subject wise by sitting in home through subject wise textbook list available in the college website.

7. Collection of Educational CD's & NPTEL Learning Resources: The library has vast collection of Soft-skill based CD's and Subject wise NPTEL video lecture CD's for student reference. Students can also copy these resources in their laptop/pen drive.
8. Collection of IIM Study materials: The college has procured ample number of Study materials from IIM (Ahmadabad) in order to sensitize the students with resources of reputed B-Schools.
9. Collection of Project Reports: The library maintains vast collection of project reports in all UG & PG programmes. These reports are available for students to refer at the time of planning their projects.
10. Availability of Digitized Textbooks for Students: Rare and expensive books are available in digitized form with the library and made available for the users for internal usage based on request.
11. Book Exhibition: Library organizes book exhibitions of various publishers for limited duration round the year where students and faculty can suggest new books to be procured and added to the collection of books in the library.

(15) Strategy Adopted to complete the curriculum

Major challenges in completing the curriculum within the planned time frame has been very unusual. However, the following precautions are taken for any deviations from the time frame:

1. Technology Based Learning:
Through promoting the use of LCD projectors in classrooms lot of time could be saved than otherwise.
 2. Teaching Plan:
This is a tool for dividing the entire syllabus in to practical classroom sessions which could anticipate the required number of classes beforehand so as to prepare students for the examination.
 3. College Calendar:
It creates an impact of time limits available for learning so that pace of the teaching is adjusted accordingly.
 4. Study Materials:
The lucidity of narration in the study material makes learning comfortable and easy for the students and to cope with time constraints.
 5. Additional Classes:
In case required , additional classes are also conducted to compensate any loss of time.
 6. Expertise of the Faculty:
The faculty are competent and experienced enough to handle such situations to complete the syllabus in time.
1. Providing Opportunity to teach new Subjects:
Teachers are encouraged to teach new subjects every year so that they enjoy the freedom of choosing the liked subjects and avoid monotony in teaching same subject for continuously for many years. This also helps in enhancing their knowledge capacities widely and make them competent.
 2. Providing support for technology based information collection:
Based on various trainings provided by the college to acquire new knowledge through technology based information collection, the obsolete methods/techniques of faculty members are removed.
 3. Recharge through incorporation of Value added Chapter in each subject:
All teachers are required to choose & teach a few sessions of value added chapter in each subject both in UG and PG programmes. This helps to enrich their job by identifying new developments in the subject.
 4. Contribute to innovative teaching Practices:
Teachers are encouraged to bring in creativity and innovation in teaching practices. Such for example, are entry test and summarizing the class by students at the end of the class, new and relevant business cases, business games etc. aimed at increased participation of students. The faculty are encouraged to demonstrate creativity and innovation in teaching.
 5. Take lead in curriculum development:
Providing opportunity to participating in curriculum development serves to recharge the teachers.
 6. Device and deliver Certificate courses:
Through Certificate programmes designed to meet the latest trends in the industry, teachers get opportunity to choose, learn and deliver subjects of their choice.
 7. Research Centre In charge:
The College has identified emerging areas for promoting research in the form of Research Centres as mentioned in the college website and expertise of the faculty is utilized in the capacity of research centre Head to pursue research in the relevant area.
 8. Study Leave:
College has a policy to grant study leave for pursuing Ph.D. research on full time. Such instances already exist.
 9. Support for Research:
The College persuades all its faculty to earn research degrees such as M.Phil. and Ph.D. Almost all have acquired M.Phil. and are doing Ph.D. on part-time.
 10. Research Grants :
The College promotes the efforts of the faculty to obtain funded projects and research grants from appropriate agencies such as UGC, DST, AICTE, ICSSR etc. The college also has a policy to provide seed money for research based on

(16) Faculty Re-charge Strategy

Details on the policies/systems are in place to recharge teachers : (e.g. providing research grants, study leave, support for research and academic publications teaching experience in other national institutions and specialized programmes industrial engagement etc.)

request.

11. 11. Teaching Experience in other National Institutions/ specialized Programmes:

The college prefers to appoint the experienced teachers who have qualified from National Institutions based on availability. The college also encourages its teachers to gain exposure by participating in various programmes held in National Institutions like IIMs, IITs, NITK etc. The college also sent 7 of its faculty members to international institutions like Grimsby Institute of Further and Higher Studies, Grimsby, U.K. and University of Singapore during last four years.

12. Industrial Engagement:

The college has appointed many teachers who have experience in industry/related fields. The college also promotes consultancy services to be taken up by the teachers so that they gain experience without being away from the job.

(17) Strategies to Improve Teachers Quality

Details of the strategies adopted by the college in planning and management of its human resource to meet the changing requirements of the curriculum are:

A. Recruitment:

The strategies adopted by the college in planning and management of its human resource is done in the following stages :

1. Identification and Announcement of Vacancy:
Whenever there is a expansion of the existing course, introduction of new course, or requirement for replacement, the college assess the knowledge, subject skill, Qualification, Specialization and experience required for the potential vacancy to be filled. Accordingly publicity is given through media, created database throughout the year, and references.
2. Obtaining Applications:
Aspirants to the vacancy will submit the applications along with their resume to the college for consideration.
3. Sorting & Short listing:
The applications obtained are processed through sorting and short listing.
4. Scrutiny for suitability:
This is particularly to maintain gender balance and matching the area of specialization.
5. Intimation to the candidates:
Short listed candidates are intimated to attend a preliminary round of discussions at college.
6. Preliminary Interviews & Discussions:
This will be held in Principal chamber along with HOD and other senior faculty.
7. Class Demonstration:
A live demonstration of the class is mandatory for satisfactory candidates based on preliminary interviews and discussions. Opinion of the students is also elicited.

8. Verification of credentials:
Credentials of successful candidates are verified before the final interview.
9. Interview:
The round table interview is conducted by representatives of the Management and the Institution and terms of employment and suitability is ascertained.
10. References:
Verification of conduct, Character, previous employment and qualifications are done through references provided by the candidate.
11. Selection & Induction:
The finally selected candidate is inducted into the new work place and acquainted with the systems and the facilities of the college and gradually absorbed into schedule of work.

B. Retention:

The management follows the below mentioned retention strategies to maintain the faculty:

- In-house faculty development programme and training programme are organized from time to time to upgrade the knowledge and skills of the faculty to meet the changing requirements of the curriculum.
- The management conducts a yearly felicitation programme and honors the faculty and non teaching staff members for the outstanding achievements during the year.
- The management felicitates faculty members who complete their M.Phil., Ph.D. or any other higher studies during the year.
- Any request for leave to do the research work has been considered on case to case basis.
- The institute provides equal opportunity to all the faculty members to grow with the institute and it provides good professional growth and development opportunities in terms of job enrichment, change in responsibilities, increments and promotions.
- A congenial organizational environment is enforced by the Principal in order to maintain a healthy collegueship and commandership.
- Academic flexibility and professional freedom is given to all the faculty members which helps them to creatively deliver the curriculum.
- The institution has a policy to fill vacant teaching positions in reasonable time. The institution also adheres to UGC/ State Govt. norms for faculty recruitment and promotion.

(18) Strategies Adopted by the Institution in Enhancing the Teacher Quality

Faculty Training programmes organized by the institution to empower and enable the use of various tools and technology for improved teaching-learning:

Teaching learning methods/approaches

The tools and techniques used for improved teaching-learning methods/approaches are as follows:

1. Teaching Plan serves as a tool for student centric teaching. The pace of teaching is synchronized with the capacity of

the learners and the time in the hand through the effective utilization of teaching plan.

2. Study Material developed according to the syllabus provides comprehensive information in easy understandable manner for the students.
3. Tutorial provides individual attention to slow learners who otherwise find inability to cope with the better performers in the class.
4. Topic based assignments to be worked and presented by the students ensure student responsibility in learning process and adherence to time schedules.
5. Progress Reports of the attendance provide caution to alert the students on punctuality to the classes. Progress reports on studies are conveyed to the students as well as their parents which helps to monitor and ensure study performance.
6. Case Analysis, Role play, Business games and simulations offer interesting ways of methods/approaches.
7. Use of Library and information through Internet are also utilized for improved teaching - learning.
8. The faculty members acquire competence in technology based data analysis through use of SPSS etc. learned through FDP programmes contributes improved teaching.
9. Faculty training programmes conducted in the institution to train the faculty in Counseling served to improve their capacity to handle students problems arising out of stress, neglect, loneliness and domestic difficulties.

Handling new curriculum:

New curriculum becomes necessary for a faculty mainly on two occasions : When there is a revision of the curriculum by the University or When a New Subject is chosen to be taught a fresh at the beginning of a particular year/semester.

1. Whenever a new Curriculum is introduced by the University, a Faculty Training Programme is organized by the institution in which details on inclusion, exclusion, weightage of each topic in the Unit, relevant references, approaches and methods, pattern of question papers, knowledge background etc. are discussed.
2. Individual faculty are required to make summary presentation on curriculum in the ensuing faculty training programmes. Such discussions are scheduled to be conducted periodically in phased manner.
3. The concerned faculty members are required to prepare teaching plan session wise and to develop study material as per the new curriculum.
4. Whenever an existing faculty takes over a new curriculum in a particular semester or year, a discussion is generated in the training programme by the senior faculty and the faculty members who have handled that subject previously. The depth and framework form the subject matter of the discussion.

Content/knowledge management:

Through Faculty Training Programmes, Faculty members will identify, acquire and transform the information in to knowledge. Identification of relevant information according to the curriculum is done through discussion in the training programme. This would include sources such as books, periodicals, journals, video clippings, databases etc. These information are acquired suitably to prepare teaching plan and study materials and transformed in the

form of lectures, PPT presentations, and other methods etc.

Selection, development and use of enrichment materials:

Faculty training programme will also provide a spectrum of supplementary materials which serves to be used as enrichment materials. Such for example are Open Source Courseware, NPTEL Lectures, Freely downloadable books from internet and other reference materials. The competency to dovetail such materials is acquired through the training programmes.

Assessment:

The faculty training programmes helps the faculty in the assessment of the students in the following ways :

- (i) Marks secured in the internal examinations
- (ii) Regularity in attending classes.
- (iii) Punctuality in submitting assignments.
- (iv) Classroom discipline.
- (v) Participative learning
- (vi) Interest and participation in co-curricular activities.
- (vii) Subject based viva-voce
- (viii) Flair in report writing
- (ix) Effective presentation
- (x) Inter-personal relations and good habits.

Cross cutting issues:

Cross-cutting issues such as gender, environment, climate change etc. are discussed in the Faculty training programme due to their significance in the present context for human subsistence and survival. Subject experts in this area are brought in to deliver speeches on relevant topics concerning the above.

Audio Visual Aids/multimedia:

Faculty training programme also contain certain sessions on usage of audio-visuals and multimedia. Live demonstrations are performed by the trainers who take care of such systems in the college.

Teaching learning material development, selection and use:

As mentioned earlier, through the training/induction programmes, faculty members develop the skill to develop and use teaching learning materials such as session wise teaching plan, study materials according to the syllabus, question bank and the business cases as well as PPT presentations to be discussed in the class.

(19) Quality Monitoring Strategy

The institutional effort to monitor and evaluate the quality of teaching learning:

1. Regular Conduct of Internal Examinations: Internal examinations are conducted for all the courses at regular intervals as planned in the academic calendar which is prepared by the HOD in consultation with the academic faculty at the beginning of the calendar year/semester.
2. Result Analysis: The results of the University examinations are analysed through segregating percentage of students in terms of achievements as reflected in their marks scored in each examination. The faculty who has been engaging classes for the concerned subjects will be responsible for the poor performance of the students.

3. Feedback From Students: The college collects feedback from students in a proper format at the end of every semester and is reviewed by the principal. This feedback is also conveyed to the concerned faculty for rectification and improvement.
4. Class Visits of Head of the Department and Principal: A direct and first hand appraisal of the classes is obtained by the HOD/Principal periodically while the classes are in progress.
5. Training of new faculty: New faculty members are provided opportunity to attend the classes of experienced faculty in order to develop competency in teaching process.
6. IQAC: IQAC closely monitors and evaluate the quality of teaching- learning processes in the college.
7. CCD Monitoring of the Classes: The college one of the beginners in using high technology to maintain discipline as well as ensure the regular classes to the students through the closed circuit Cameras.
8. Students Opinion Through Suggestion box: Students who hesitate to open-up in other forums can make use of the suggestion box inter alia the quality of teaching of the various subjects.
9. End User benefit Documentation: Through a new practice of monitoring the classes in progress, by visiting the classes during every hour and recording the signature of faculty in the classes ensures that the end users are benefitted.

(20) Faculty Evaluation Strategy used for Improving the Quality of the Teaching-Learning Process

The Institute has a format for regular teacher evaluation by the students at the end of each semester. Various parameters like (i) Regularity in conducting classes, (ii) Time -consciousness, (iii) Preparation for the Classes, (iv) Syllabus completion in time, (v) Competency in the subject concerned, (vi) Presentation skill (Voice, Language, Clarity), (vii) Methodology in Teaching, (viii) Interaction with the students, (ix) Accessibility to the students outside the class, (x) Quality & understandability of Study Materials etc., related to quality of teaching - learning process are incorporated in the format. The feedback grade points of all faculty members are worked out and conveyed as a feedback to individual teachers. Based on the feedback as a guideline, the faculty members set new approaches and methods to improve the quality of teaching -learning process. The external peers have an opportunity to give their feedback in the form of suggestions through the suggestion box kept in the college.

The Institution has a mechanism of self evaluation of teachers to identify their involvement and contribution to various activities related to teaching, learning and research. The motivation for improved performance is incorporated into the remuneration system. The College website also provides scope for registering the feedback by external peers and alumni.

(21) Curriculum Enrichment Strategies

The following are the efforts made by the institution to modify,

enrich and organize the curriculum to enhance the experience of the students with needs of the dynamic employment market :

- Case Study Development: Students are given opportunity to extract real life context from organizations where they visit either for field practicum of research project work or summer placement and these are worked out into case studies through group exercises under the guidance of the faculty supervisors. This enables to enrich and organize the curriculum beyond routine classroom learning through lecture, and improve the dynamism and competitiveness of the students in the employment market.
- Group Discussions: Topics of monotonous nature are divided to be discussed among students in groups and generate ideas in line with their experience and viewpoints. These discussions are guided by the faculty to retain the curriculum relevance. Ultimately, group presentations lead to encouragement of students initiatives and leadership qualities which are the focus in the employment markets.
- Simulation: Efforts are made to utilize simulation techniques to reproduce real life situations in classroom. Students develop ability for positive responses in problem solving and decision making.
- Laboratory based learning: Students are encouraged to utilize various Application software in computer laboratory. They are also trained to develop reports using various statistical analysis and data management & interpretation packages through network based learning.
- Field work based learning: Fieldwork has the potential to enrich the curriculum combining the experiences of the students with concept based theoretical learning.

This takes place in the following ways:

1. Discussion with industry expert.
2. Data collection/information gathering in the process of research project preparation.
- Exposure based learning: Through study tour, industry visits and interaction with resource persons. exposure based learning will provide the techniques of resource mobilization, quality production, marketing strategies, customer satisfaction and Human resource management in business.
- Research based Learning: Undertaking research projects as part of course requirement enables students with adequate know-how on application of alternative solutions to social context.
- Experiential Learning: Students of both UG and PG programmes conduct programs such as marketing exhibition, Online virtual investment, Business model competitions, and group discussion. Programs such as Manegma – National Level Conference on selected Themes of Business Management, MAGMA-Management Feast, MATRIX- International Business Case Presentation, MEGA-INDIA – Indian Industry Study, Manthana – An Intellectual churning of Social work Fraternity, ESPERANZA – An IT Fest, etc.
- Student Forum Based Activities: Various student forums like HR Forum, Marketing Forum, Finance Forum, IT Forum are also providing opportunity for students to creatively reflect their experiences and integrating with it curriculum.

- Entrepreneurship Development Cell: A separate cell for entrepreneurship development is incorporated in the college. This cell creates awareness of need and relevance of entrepreneurship as career option among the students thereby strengthening their Entrepreneurship skills.
- Team Work Activities: Students of the College plan and organize various social programs like Teachers Day Celebration, Onam Celebration, Iftar Party, Karnataka Rajyothsava etc.
- Idea Creation through Marketing Exhibition: MBA, BBM and B.Com students involve in creating new business models/Ideas in Teams of 4-5 students and present their model in Marketing Exhibition conducted by the respective Departments. This kind of practical learning through Idea creation leads to innovation in business models/marketing ideas.

(22) Strategy of Introducing New Programmes/courses

Bachelor of Commerce (B.Com.) has been introduced the academic year 2013-14 in the institution. The rationale behind are following:

- Student preference
- Demand by the parents and employers.
- Financial viability
- Job and Higher education Opportunities
- Availability of Expertise
- Infrastructural readiness
- Uncertainty of persisting demand for other courses like BBM
- Future plans of the institution such as starting the post graduate course in the subject.
- Availability of easy finance from the banks for poor students.
- Priority for consideration for female students.
- Affordability of the local population
- Huge requirement of professionals in Banking and related field at national level

(23) Innovations in Teaching & Learning

1. The institution provides opportunity to all kind of students who have a strong desire to change in their life through its "First Come First Serve" model.
2. Through our pedagogy of "Student Support Model" students are encouraged to be achievers. This include a unique way of handling each class with "Entry Test" at the beginning and "Summarizing the Class" at the end.
3. "Save a Year program" allows the students to enhance the attendance by taking additional classes in a given subject so that a student who has attendance between 50 to 60% can save a year. This facility is available only once in 3 years for Undergraduate students. This is an opportunity to the students to realize their mistake and to continue in the mainstream.
4. Economically poor students are supported by providing "Earn while Learn" Program. This is intended to be achieved through taking up part-time jobs either in the college or outside through reference.
5. Competency of the students are enhanced by providing "Value Added Chapter" in all subjects in each semester.
6. Teaching - Learning process is made more realistic by providing "High Tech Class Rooms" with LCD projector, audio amplifier, Wi-Fi based Internet facility and CCD Camera

Monitoring in all class rooms.

7. The Institute provides "Student Supportive Materials" like College Calendar, Teaching Plan booklet, Study materials, Question Bank of all subjects, Career guidance for redefining the goal in the beginning of each semester.
8. The Institute also provides "Web Supportive Materials" like Old Question papers, College Magazine & News Letters, Placement brochure, Notice Board, Higher Education & Job Opportunities which can be downloaded by the students from the website of the college.
9. "New technologies" like Biometric attendance for Staff members, CCD camera recording to monitor student discipline are deployed by the institution to enhance student learning.
10. The college website supplements the teaching - learning process.
11. Indigenous software development by Students for internal Institutional requirement.
12. MOU/Collaboration with local IT companies on student support for system development.
13. Mentoring Program : The faculty members mentor the students and connect with them on academic & personal aspects on a regular basis.
14. Regular subscription of leading business news papers for each and every student and weekly news analysis.

(24) Strategy of Starting New Courses

Autonomy to the organization to start new courses with increased job opportunities or with job oriented curriculum will attract more students and hence the demand for admission will increase. For example, Bachelor in commerce (B.Com.) and Master in commerce (M.Com.) with Chartered Accountant curriculum will attract students who have career objective of auditing profession.

(25) Improvement in Education Model

Compared to presently dominated credit based system and improvement in this system as choice based credit system, the competency based system getting attraction by student learners. In such competency based higher education model, students can earn for their work based on their smartness and enhance their skills. Because many competency-based education (CBE) programmes have been designed to allow students to learn and progress at their own pace, students with learning from life and work experience can save considerable time in earning a degree. In addition, some of the newest CBE models have leveraged technology in order to lower the cost. But above all, CBE programs are designed to improve the quality of higher education by putting the focus squarely on demonstrated learning outcomes. Such improvements in education model will also enhance students admission to the college.

(26) Improvement in Examination System

Continuous evaluation in higher education system is the present requirement to remove the fear of annual or semester end examination. Autonomy in designing the examination system and improvement from present pattern of closed book examination to either open book examination or objective type multiple choice examination pattern will release the tension of remembering entire book and hence becomes popular system among the students.

Conclusions

Formulation and implementation of some of the above strategies in the college resulted in improved quality of education, improved student discipline, improved student attitude towards regularity in attending the classes, improved examination performance and hence the standard of the students. This also improved the satisfaction level of all the stakeholders and enhanced the name and fame of the institution. The institutional strategy of such value addition through good number of innovations supported the brand building and hence improved demand for admission.

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Conflict of interests

The author declare that he has no competing interest.

References

1. Cathy Hall, William Swart, and Steve Duncan, 2012, Balancing Customer needs and standards in Higher Education, *Quality Approaches in Higher Education*, 3, 1, 2-7.
2. Douglas C. Bennett, 2001, "Assessing Quality in Higher Education," *Liberal Education*, Spring 2001, 40-46.
3. Harvey L. and Green D., 1993, "Defining Quality," *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, 18, 1, 9-34.
4. Hill, F. (1995). *Managing service quality in higher education: the role of the student as primary consumer*. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 3 No. 3, pp. 10-21.
5. Hill, Y., Lomas, L., MacGregor, J., 2003, Students perceptions of quality in higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 11, 1, 15-20.
6. Joseph, M., Yakhou, M., Stone, G., 2005, An educational institutions quest for service quality: customers perspective. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 13, 1, 66-82.
7. Kotler, P., 1985. *Strategic Marketing for Educational Institutions*, Prentice-Hall, London.
8. Manual for self-study report of Affiliated colleges, 2013, National Assessment and Accreditation Council. Downloaded from www.naac.gov.in, referred on 12/04/2015.
9. O Neill, M. A. and Palmer, A., 2004, Importance-performance analysis: a useful tool for directing continuous quality improvement in higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 1, 1, 39-52.
10. Srikanthan, G., Dalrymple, J., 2002, Developing a holistic model for quality in higher education. *Quality in Higher Education*, 8, 3, 215-224.
11. Srikanthan, G., Dalrymple, J., 2003,. Developing alternative perspectives for quality in higher education. *International Journal of Education Management*, 17, 3, 126-136.
12. Wright C, and O'Neil M. A., 2002, Service Quality in the Higher Education Sector: An Empirical Investigation of Students' Perceptions, *Higher Education Research and Development*, 21, 1, 23-29.

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